

IMPLEMENTATION OF DEVICE AUTHENTICATION IN WIRELESS NETWORKS

Archana K, Archana M N, Architha Shastry P , Chaithra N T

Dept of IS&E, NIE, Mysore, India

Under the guidance of

Mrs. C K Vanamala

Asst. Professor, Dept of IS & E
NIE, MYSORE, INDIA

Abstract:

In day-to-day life, providing security for devices is very important as the intruders are finding ways to access the data in networks especially in wireless networks. When the communication takes place between two or more devices and if the devices are not authenticated, then it becomes very easy for the intruders to access the data that leads to fatal circumstances. This situation needs to be tackled and a solution is to be provided. So, we propose and implement a simple, efficient authentication mechanism wherein the devices authenticated at first and then the user in a particular group will be authenticated to share data or information.

Keywords: Authentication, Smart Card, Seed Box, Nonce Process, OTP

Section 1

INTRODUCTION

Wireless Internet access technology is being increasingly deployed in both office and public environments, as well as by internet users at home.

*Security in Computer world determines the ability of the system to manage, protect and distribute sensitive information. Security cannot rely on central servers, as there are no guarantees that they will be in radio range all times - devices' availability and motion are quite unpredictable in mobile ad hoc networks.

* Authentication for Devices is a new technique to provide security for networks. This project proposes and implements a device authentication mechanism in which the devices that need to communicate with each other must belong to the same group and should be authenticated for communication by using Shamir's secret sharing algorithm.

Section 2

LITERATURE SURVEY

2.1 Device Authentication Using Novel Smart Card Software [10]

It is a simple device authentication framework which provides device-oriented authentication and authorization mechanisms for non-PC Internet-ready information appliances. The purpose of the framework is to prevent device spoofing, and to restrict unauthorized access to the device in a future ubiquitous network. Here the smart card will be attached to a device such as an information appliance. *Disadvantage:* If the card gets tampered or damaged then the device authentication will be a problem in this system.

2.2 Gesture based user authentication and face recognition system [11]

Here the user authentication is based on gestures and facial expression captured by a video camera. Unlike pure biometrics, such as fingerprints, iris scans, and faces, gesture-based authentication combines irrevocable biometric information, such as the shapes and relative sizes of body parts, with voluntary movements which can be revoked. *Disadvantage:* Movements and expressions need not always be same. So authentication using this method is not reliable.

Section 3 SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig 3a System Architecture

3.1 Device authentication and group authentication

Each device in a group should be registered from the seedbox separately. Once the registration is successful each device will be having preshared key within it. When two devices trying to communicate for any data exchange then we should allow only those devices within the group using nonce process. So that even though devices are “authenticated, it requires to authorise” for data exchange. This is shown in the figure Fig 3a.

- Seedbox performs Group Creation in that process, admin should give Group name & Group key and for each group, 'N' number of polynomials will be generated.
- Seedbox is responsible to view requests and take appropriate action.
- Client node send a registration request for a particular group to seedbox/admin by providing its MACID, Owner Name and Group Name.
- Once the node approved for a particular group by the seedbox and get its key-value pairs, a node should be authorized to communicate with another node which is of same group.

3.2 User authentication

- Through login id and password, user authentication is done.

3.3 Modules used

The proposed mechanism should be placed between the internal system (e.g. software application) and the external communication (e.g. wireless interfaces), as a security

middleware. The figure 3a shows the architecture of the proposed mechanism and its internal building blocks.

- The *Seed Box* is a storage unit responsible to hold all known pre-shared keys *kn*, where each *kn* corresponds to one different *secure cluster*. Each *kn* receives a mnemonic name, assigned by the device's owner, to be easily associated to a *secure cluster*.
- The *I/O* is the building block responsible for the communication of the mechanism with the

network communication interfaces (the layer just below the mechanism).

- The *Control Unit* involves the functions, wherein a device enrolls itself for authentication (which involves nonce process which means generation of an arbitrary number called cipher text) for the purpose of communication.
- Shamir's Secret Sharing (SSS) implementation for secure key, authentication and Validation process.
- One Time password (OTP) is used to generate a challenge message.
- For encryption and decryption we use Symmetric CIPHERING.

Section 4

HARDWARE AND SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS

4.1 Hardware requirements

- 2GB RAM
- 80GB Hard Disk
- Pentium IV and above processor
- At least 4 machines , 1 for administrator, 2 from one group cluster and another from different group cluster

4.2 Software requirements

- Operating System: Windows Version
- Software : Visual Studio 2010
- Language : C#
- Application : Windows Forms

Section 5

SYSTEM DESIGN

System design is the process of defining the architecture, components, modules, interfaces, and data for a system satisfy specified requirements. It implies a systematic and rigorous approach to design.

6.1.2 Remote Registration

In the beginning the device requests for the registration by sending its MAC id, group name to which it wants to join. This information is sent to seed box or admin for the approval.

Fig 6.1.2a Node Remote Registration Snapshot

6.1.3 View Request

The admin can view the pending request and can either approve, reject, delete the request.

Fig 6.1.3a View Request Snapshot

6.1.4 Join Group

Join Group screen displays list of IP address and corresponding group name. The Group Joining process is done between the two nodes which are in same group and without the interaction of SEEDBOX or ADMIN. Clicking on the IP address of the device allows the further communication with it.

Fig 6.1.4a Join Group Snapshot

Fig 6.1.4b Further Communication Snapshot

Fig 6.1.4b Further Communication Snapshot

Section 7

CONCLUSION

The authentication mechanism provided eases out the work of the people who spend a lot of time in monitoring their devices. The proposed mechanism thwarts security attacks, such as Man in the Middle (MitM) and replay attacks. The proposed mechanism is not only an ad hoc networks secure solution, and can be set on any kind of computer networks, offering a light and distributed security solution.

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